

FRIEDRICH NIETZSCHE ON AESTHETIC EXPERIENCE AND THE PHENOMENON OF DEPRESSION

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 19

Issue 8

Pages: 881-892

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1808

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11177072

Manuscript Accepted: 04-15-2024

Friedrich Nietzsche on Aesthetic Experience and the Phenomenon of Depression

Ypril James F. Cabasag*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

Basically, humans desire nothing but to be happy. Humans exert much effort to make their lives meaningful and worth living. For humans, obtaining the meaning of existence is the foundation of happiness. However, despite humans' desire to be happy, an ugly truth still remains: life is a tragedy. Friedrich Nietzsche argues that life is a constant struggle and that to live is to suffer. By seeing this ugly picture of life, humans gradually fall into depression. "Depression is a common mental disorder that presents with depressed mood, loss of interest or pleasure . . . and may lead to suicide (WHO, 2021)." More so, science contends that specific brain dysfunctions cause depression, and various solutions are offered to address this, like taking anti-depressants and undergoing psychotherapy, but amidst all these, depression remains. In this case, what other means can be utilized to address the problem of depression? Using the philosophical-qualitative method, this paper will attempt to address the perennial issue of depression. This paper attempts to understand the problem of depression by tracing it to the degradation of meaning and will resolve it by explaining the essential role aesthetics plays in man's existence.

Keywords: *meaning of existence, tragedy, depression, science, anti-depressant, psychotherapy, aesthetic/art, Apollo, Dionysus, Ubermensch, will to power*

Introduction

Human existence is not a one-dimensional reality, it is comprised of various aspects, like social, political, spiritual, physical and psychological, given all of these aspects, man lives not just to meet what life requires of him, but to transform the very life he possesses into something meaningful. It can be argued that man is in constant search for happiness. However, happiness can be defined in multiple ways. Every man has his own means of making himself happy. A rich and a poor may have different means of achieving happiness. The happiness of a man who gives supremacy to his reason may differ from a man who values his emotions. Regardless of the ways, what matters is the goal of making the self happy. Every endeavor of man is an effort towards reaching happiness. The very idea of happiness is a reflection of man's effort to transform his existence into something meaningful.

In Aristotle's work, *Nicomachean Ethics*, he speaks of "Eudaimonia" or happiness as the highest good for the human beings (Grech, 2019, p. 47). However, Aristotle does not speak of happiness as a kind of emotional state, rather he refers "happiness as an end of good and fulfilling life" (Ryan, & Mortela, n.d., p. 2). Here, man is called to truly live well, which is only possible if man makes himself virtuous, because for Aristotle, "virtue is the central part of eudaimonia" (Bartlett & Collins, 2012, p. x, cited in Ryan & Mortela, n.d., p. 7). For Aristotle, by embracing a virtuous existence, meaning can be achieved. Virtue is necessary in order for man to be truly happy, it can be argued that by living a virtuous life, man can fulfill his own meaning.

Meaning is integral in the very essence of man. The truth is, what places man at the peak in the hierarchy of beings is, aside from his capacity of rationalize, man can obtain his meaning. Like Aristotle, Abraham Maslow, a prominent figure in the field of psychology, also argues that man desires to acquire meaning. However, what separates Maslow from Aristotle is that, Maslow argues that meaning can only be possible by reaching the point of self-actualization. Aristotle argues that only by possessing virtues that meaning is possible, however for Maslow, the key to meaning is to provide to oneself all the necessary elements of life. These elements of life are referred to as Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs. As Maslow explains, person's entire existence is divided into different needs which he has to achieve to find fulfillment, from person's basic needs- physical needs, going upward, to none visible needs, like security, care and love, and the peak, self-actualization. Thus, Abraham Maslow argues that when one of the needs is not achieved, humans would never be fulfilled. It is therefore parallel to saying that when a person fails to achieve what he desires to achieve, the opposite of meaning may appear, "depression," or the "sense of meaninglessness."

As basically conceived, depression is considered as a "mental problem" which primarily affects the mental capacity of man and is channeled into his actual behavioral system showing a sort of withdrawal from the world. As understood by World Health Organization (2012), "depression is a common mental disorder that presents with depressed mood, loss of interest or pleasure, decreased energy, feelings of guilt or low self-worth, disturbed sleep or appetite, and poor concentration . . . and may lead to suicide." Many people today do experience and battle this problem. The alarming reality is, depression does not only occur to adults, but even to the younger ones, as early as childhood stage. According to the data, "depression is estimated to affect 350 million people" (WHO, 2012). "Depressive disorders often start at a young age; they reduce people's functioning and often are recurring. For these reasons, depression is the leading cause of disability worldwide in terms of total years lost due to disability. The demand for curbing depression and other mental health conditions is on the rise globally" (WHO, 2012).

Philosophically speaking, there is no exact account that gives specific explanation regarding depression. However, philosophy has unearthed some similar ideas like "angst," "meaninglessness of life," "life is absurd," "life is suffering," and the like. As philosophy

purports, these concepts unveil one of the truths about human existence, and that is, pain is an inevitable human reality. Nevertheless, these concepts must not and should not be understood as they are. Under philosophical paradigm, these concepts must be viewed as essential springboards in finding the very essential things in life. Philosophy treats these ideas not as end but as means in seeing and understanding life as what it truly is and possibly leads the person's unfolding of meaning. The occurrence of depression possibly reveals a greater truth about human life and so, requires man's attention.

Finding the true meaning of life is considered as the very spirit of philosophical enterprise. As what Socrates says, an "unexamined life is not worth living." But this ideology did not only rest on Socrates himself; it continued to flourish reaching the time of post-modernism and contemporary period. One of the post-modern thinkers who tried to revive what the ancient philosophers once valued was Friedrich Nietzsche. In one of Nietzsche's most famous works, *The Birth of Tragedy*, Nietzsche argues that tragedy, an ancient form of Greek drama, is a concrete reflection of human existence, as it is the Greek drama that shows what life truly is, both suffering and pain (Maboloc, 2013, p.41). Nietzsche shares the same view with Schopenhauer that life is full of suffering, to be a man is to suffer to certain degree (Maboloc, 2013, p.41). Pessimist philosophers, in fact, continue to argue that life is continuous cycle of pain and suffering. However, Nietzsche argues that human suffering can be redeemed through art (Maboloc, 2013, p.44). Nietzsche purports that most philosophers, especially those who belong in the tradition of modernism have denounced the relevance of human sensuous drive as it can only distort the way humans see themselves. As mentioned by Heidegger, "the advent of modernity saw the world as separate from man. Science has claimed a strong authoritative position about the nature of things so that before anything is judged as true, it needs to be tested by the instrument of scientific research (Maboloc, 2013, p.14). Nietzsche himself, however, opposed this contention. He had seen that there was still something beyond science that could explain the truth about human life. He believed that the other alternative to understand what truly life is all about is through "art" (Maboloc, 2013, p.45). Through "aesthetic experience", Nietzsche was convinced that life is in itself an "art." Nietzsche argued that life couldn't be objectified by reason. For Nietzsche, it is with aesthetic lens that life could be justly examined.

It is truly an undeniable fact that the phenomenon of depression has become an issue today that calls for an immediate solution. Medical experts contend that the emergence of depression is due to a chemical imbalance that takes place in a person's brain. Various medical solutions are offered to mend depression, amidst all these, why are there still so many people suffering from depression? This reality only reveals one thing, the field of medical science fails to truly understand the root of depression. This paper intends to give a critique into how science and even psychology understand the issue of depression, as well as to show how these fields failed in their approaches to address the problem. Using the lens of Nietzsche's Aesthetic Experience, this paper aims to place depression in the right perspective by tracing the problem of depression to man's search for meaning.

Research Questions

This paper intends to contribute an intellectual as well as philosophical understanding and solution to the ever-growing problem of depression. Hence, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is depression and how has it been treated by medical science and psychology?
2. Are the solutions provided by medical science and psychology enough to understand the problem of depression?
3. What does Nietzsche mean by aesthetic experience and how can it be achieved?
4. Can Friedrich Nietzsche's aesthetic experience be the answer to the human person's problem as he or she aims to redeem himself or herself from depression?

Methodology

This inquiry is a philosophical one, that is why, it primarily uses a philosophical-qualitative approach as research method. In this paper, there are two fundamental concepts involved, first is phenomenon of depression, embracing both the psychological and medical perspective and second is Friedrich Nietzsche's notion of aesthetic experience. This paper attempts to understand the problem of depression by tracing it to the degradation of meaning and will resolve it by explaining the essential role that aesthetics plays in man's existence.

More so, the following sequence will be done, first—the researcher will elucidate the concept of depression, second – he lay down the foundation why man gets depressed, third—the researcher will lay down and explain the philosophy of Nietzsche on "aesthetic experience" and lastly—the researcher will address the problem of depression using Nietzsche's aesthetic experience. It has to be noted that since this paper is a philosophical paper, no survey or interview will be conducted and therefore does not involve any respondent and research instrument.

Procedure

This paper is text-based, meaning it is based on what is written on books and other printed sources; no interview, survey, and other quantitative procedures are needed. Instead, the researcher would spend most of his time in this inquiry reading, understanding, and analyzing books and other relevant references found in the school library and on online journal sites.

Results and Discussion

Depression is one of the most common and rampant mental problems that gives much burden to people from any age group today. According to existentialist philosophers, humans are thrown into the world, this idea paves the way for humans to look for the very sense of existence. With this, a man becomes an active being, a being who creates. Humans have realized that to make sense of their very existence; they have to create. Human is not thrown in an abyss, instead, of in a specific space, the world. The existence of humans in the world reveals humans' every possibility and limit. The reality of the world and humans' ability to create give birth to meaning. Meaning gives sense to a human's very existence. All human efforts are geared towards quenching their thirst for meaning.

Existentialist thinkers like Soren Kierkegaard, Jean Paul Sartre, Martin Heidegger and others have argued that the world has no original meaning and upon seeing this, man faces a kind of existential dread. The fundamental problem that existentialism leaves man to resolve is the problem of meaninglessness. The absurdity of the world leads man to question the worth of his or her own existence. That is why, the danger about the problem of meaning as Albert Camus (1995) writes "there is but one truly serious philosophical problem and that is suicide" (p. 3, cited in Hassell, 2017, p. 7). The meaninglessness of existence, its absurdity, all of its tragedy turn man hopeless, as this becomes man's inescapable reality as Schopenhauer notes it. Is there nothing in existence than its meaninglessness? Though it is true that suicide is always the possibility, yet this is only the result of man's failure to look for his own resolve given the absurdity of his own existence. It simply entails that for the existentialist philosophers, the meaninglessness does not necessarily mean the fixed destiny of man, because for them, the conceived meaninglessness gives man an opportunity to discover and craft his own. It allows man to pioneer his own meaning. The nihilistic attitude of the existentialist thinkers is necessary to promote their optimistic intentions. For existentialist thinkers meaning is something that an individual must work on.

However, attaining purpose or meaning is no ordinary task; it requires man to exhaust all his possessed energy. To achieve meaning only entails man to have a holistic grasp of the very reality of his existence. It is indispensable for a man to make sense of everything around him, for meaning is revealed in only such a way. Here, the problem of depression can be traced to existentialism's problem of meaning.

Parallel to a human's longing for meaning is a desire to obtain the good while existing. It is natural for a man to envision a kind of life he wants to live. What truly matters in life is man and only man alone. Man must live a life that he truly designs. It is human to desire what is suitable for himself and live according to his set aspirations. It could be asked, is there a person who dreams what is not good for him? Only when the good has achieved that meaning is possible.

Moreover, humans' very encounter with existence reveals that life is not all the time lends man what is good. The reality of human existence is ugly, and it is something inevitable. If man's only desire is good and considers it the ground where meaning lies, what will happen if life's ugly reality strikes? As Tim Ruggiero (2001) has claimed, "every time man examines the external world, it cannot be denied that there are a lot of things which man could consider condemnable, thus, these may lead him to conclude that his very existence is absurd." Here, when man who desires nothing but what is good in life has become fully awake and therefore able to see the ugly truth of existence, how to face it would become a real dilemma, and failing to address this dilemma would pull man down into the realm of despair.

Gholipour (2017) explains, "depression is a mental health condition characterized by deep sadness, loneliness and despair affecting the over-all function of a person and in worst case leads to suicide." Based on the data gathered by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2012), "more or less 350 million people around the world are experiencing depression or had experienced depression." It cannot be denied that depression has become a worldwide phenomenon and has become one of the leading causes of death worldwide due to suicide. For some, committing suicide is superficial and irrational; nevertheless, those devoured by depression are convinced that this is the least they can do. Depressed individuals feel that they are in a battle that is impossible to win. Depressed individuals believe that life is pointless. For them, life is complicated and so condemn their existence. As mentioned by Routledge (as quoted by Livni, 2019), "the very cause of depression is not the lack of adequate mental health or its absence, instead by a contemporary crisis—the crisis of meaninglessness." If the problem of depression has something to do with a person's search for meaning, it can be argued that depression is a kind of force that calls and allows man to examine and understand his existence deeply. The reality of depression may reveal to humans a greater truth about their very existence.

Friedrich Nietzsche shares the same thought with Schopenhauer and Buddha that life is filled with suffering and absurdity. Nietzsche himself sees life as tragedy. He is deeply influenced not only by Schopenhauer and Buddha but also by Greek literature. Nietzsche sees the Greek literature as the reflection of the very reality of human existence, a kind of existence filled with horror and terror, thus for Nietzsche, human is a suffering being. This thought of Nietzsche affirms the claim of Tim Ruggiero, that there are many things in life that man finds detestable, and these things has led man to find his very existence absurd. The reality of suffering is the fundamental cause why a man gradually loses his interest in life that leads to depression. If life is just all good, existence is an experience of paradise. However, humans witness the very opposite. What man sees, as he exists is life's ugly truth. Man has realized that his efforts to be happy are merely temporal. For Aristotle by becoming virtuous, man can achieve "eudemonia," however, is becoming virtuous enough to stand in the face of absurdity? Man thinks that the experience of happiness can mask the reality of human suffering, but the more man desires to be satisfied, the more it reveals to him the opposite. Man realizes that to suffer is always an unavoidable possibility, and

upon seeing this, man concludes that existence is nonsense, and so despairs. Here, even how virtuous a man becomes, if he or she does not know how to deal with the tragedy of life, depression is always a possibility.

What is the easiest way to free oneself from depression? In *The Birth of Tragedy*, Nietzsche has (1872/2003) cited Silenus' wisdom, "that given the reality of human suffering, the best thing is not to be born, and the second-best is to die soon" (p. 12). Actually, why is suicide a tendency for those who experience depression? It is because it is the easiest way to ease all life's absurdity. Too many depressed persons are persuaded that when their very existence ends, their tormenting life also ends. If a person could just have a glimpse of what truly life is before his birth, perhaps, he would choose not to be born at all. However, the reality of birth is a facticity; it is something a person did not choose for himself. For Nietzsche, given this truth about existence, humans have no choice but to confront it, to take courage and face life as it is. Nietzsche's pointless reality is not the reality of the tragic life but the human's lack of strength to face this truth of life. For Nietzsche, it makes no sense to deny and resist the horrific face of life, for if man does, the more he despairs, the more life becomes burdensome. Resisting against the ugliness of life would only worsen man's condition. Nietzsche argues that the best way to overcome the tragic life is to embrace and live it. If for a depressed person, suicide is the best way to end things, for Nietzsche, this is an act of cowardice; it only shows his lack of strength to face life. Suicide for Nietzsche is a kind of resignation and hopelessness, it does not solve the riddle. Desperation only shows that humans fail to be the master of their fate. For Nietzsche, the true essence of being human lies in the ability to face life amidst its odds and eventually, will emerge victoriously.

As clearly explained in the previous chapter, the pains of life are not just necessarily destructions but essential materials for becoming; Nietzsche has this very nourishing view about life. His pessimistic vision of life leads him to understand life holistically and treat it positively. Depression only becomes a problem when a man allows himself to be eaten by it and surrenders. But when man learns how to fight, take courage and face the perils of life, depression becomes a gateway for overriding oneself and even existence in general. Nietzsche (1872/2003) writes, "how the entire world of torment is necessary so that through it, the individual is pushed to create the redemptive vision" (p. 14). It is essential for a depressed person to acknowledge that what truly defines existence is its terror, and to resist it makes no sense. The best thing human should do is to embrace this fact and learn how to deal with it. Depression consumes humans because they cannot accept the ugly truth of life.

In today's context, science has become the leading discipline when it comes to excavating new knowledge. Most of the things that people have and enjoy now are outputs of science. It seems that science has penetrated almost all dimensions of human life. Innovations brought by science allow it to earn its reputation and has become a superior body of knowledge. When it comes to the phenomenon of depression, science has its own explanation. It contends that the fundamental cause of depression is the chemical/hormonal imbalance in the human brain. When the equilibrium of the brain is disturbed, depression occurs. As explained by Iyer and Khan, depression happens because the level of neurotransmitters and neurotransmission of the brain becomes low; it is only when this problem is addressed that depression ends. What answer does science provide for depression? It is by prescribing a sort of intake medicine called "antidepressant." As the National Institute for Mental Health believes, an antidepressant can work well to treat depression. Iyer and Khan have written that the therapeutic impact of taking an antidepressant is on neurotransmitters and neurotransmission. Furthermore, aside from taking an antidepressant, science has also come up with the use of "cranial electrical stimulation" and "electroconvulsive therapy." As explained, these two methods use electricity to stimulate the brain and restore the brain's normal function. These procedures are conducted as substitutes for pills. But amidst all these breakthrough, a question remains, are these solutions enough to truly resolve the phenomenon of depression?

It has to be noted that Nietzsche has been so critical about science, and in fact, his entire philosophical project is an exodus from science. Fundamentally, what Nietzsche dislikes about science is that science has become the embodiment of modernity. As explained, Nietzsche sees modernity as the monopolist of knowledge. This view has been extended to science because science also desires to establish universal truth. Science here is considered as an offshoot of modernity. Science believes that anything can be reduced into scientific inquiry—the use of observation and experimentation, and with such, whatever is not scientific is unreliable and doubtful. This understanding of how things should be understood springs from over-emphasizing the value of human reason. It is believed that reason is the sole source of knowledge. However, for Nietzsche (1896/1976), this contention remains nonsensical, because for him, "one might invent such a fable and yet he still would not have adequately illustrate how miserable, how shadowy and transient, how aimless and arbitrary the human intellect looks within nature" (p. 1). Nietzsche wants to convey that human intellect is just a tiny particle of the vast reality of nature, and what intellect knows is merely rabble. Just like Kant and Hume, Nietzsche argues that man cannot know the objects in themselves. The only data man could possess about things is based on his perception and not things. What is considered truth is tied on how humans could make sense of things and not really the truth in itself. As written, "does nature not conceal most things from him—even concerning his own body—in order to confine and lock him within a proud, deceptive consciousness, aloof from the coils of the bowels. The rapid flow of blood stream, and the intricate quivering of the fibers. She threw away the key" (Nietzsche, 1896/1976, p. 2).

In shedding light on the phenomenon of depression, science has taken the lead. The advancement of science convinced people to embrace the scientific approach to understand and end this problem. But considering Nietzsche's critique on science, what science has known about depression is not the truth about the matter, instead of a mere description of the case. When science says that depression is caused by a particular chemical imbalance occurring in the human brain, science only describes the physiological mechanism happening in the brain when someone experiences depression and not really why it takes place. In fact, what does man know about the

physiological structure of man? Though it is true that science can observe even the smallest particle present in the human body, yet the truth and mystery of those particles remain hidden to man. When science claims a fact about how things works, it actually refers to facts created by science and not the truth of the thing itself. It can be argued that what science has claimed about depression is only scientifically created truth.

It has to be noted that depression is not the cause itself, nor the brain causes its chemical imbalance. The chemical imbalance that occurs in the brain is the brain's reaction to something. To speak philosophically, depression has something to do with man's problem of meaning. As explained, man gets depressed because he or she has realized that life is ugly and by this, loses his or her sight of the self which is tantamount to the losing of meaning. How can science fill in the emptiness in man caused by life's ugly reality? Can the act of taking anti-depressant as well as subjecting man to electric shock restore the meaning that is lost? Bringing this issue to Nietzsche's concern, what is responsible for the loss of meaning is science itself. Because of the objectification of the world, by reducing almost everything into facts and thus forces man to conform to the system, man gradually lose his identity, he loses his power to explore his own mystery. The act of science of reducing man into scientific fragments is a violation of man's very dynamic nature. Thus, prescribing pills and electric shocks to a depressed person does not solve the problem, instead suppress it. It may be true that taking pills or electric shock would restore the brain's chemical imbalance and may subside the feeling of being low, yet it does not guarantee that it would fully address the problem. For Nietzsche, to speak of depression as a mere chemical imbalance of the brain is a very superficial understanding of the matter. The phenomenon of depression as grounded on the problem of meaning is supposed to restore man's creative ability and power to curve his or her own meaning. However, science kills such ability. Science has misunderstood the issue that lies under depression, as it tends to categorize depression as neurotic disease.

As discussed in the previous part of the paper, for Eli Siegel (as cited in Reiss, 2019), "psychiatry fails to fully understand what depression is, Siegel argues that because of lack of knowledge, and by prescribing shock treatments and drug medication, many people have suffered, and it is wrong to speak of depression as biochemically caused." The scientific approach and remedies for depression do not truly solve the problem, instead making it worse. A research conducted by Harvard University has found out that, "people don't begin to feel better after several weeks after taking medication . . . if depression were primarily the result of low level of neurotransmitters, why people don't feel better as soon as levels of neurotransmitters increase?" (health.harvard.edu, 2009). In addition, intake of medical drugs might have possible side effects on humans, in fact for Bongiorno (2015), "drugs carry with them an increase in all-cause mortality, an increased likelihood of many other problems and side effects that impair the quality of life." Because of the kind of reputation science has established and its objective findings, most people believe in what science can offer. Since people are convinced that what science offers has passed through rigorous scientific study, its ability to bring healing is at a high percentage; that is why people would think that the more they take antidepressants, the more they could recover.

However, depression is not merely a disease that falls under the realm of science; it should not be categorized as one of the physiological dysfunction. Depression, as argued, is a kind of existential agony. Fixing depression by taking anti-depressant, obviously does not truly touch the real problem. Anti-depressants do not and cannot restore what has been lost in man – meaning, instead deprive man of such. As science prescribes pills to man with depression, what science does is distorting how man sees the self. Taking anti-depressant implants man an illusory vision of the self. What science offers by taking anti-depressant is an escape from the very reality of existence. Further, the tragic existence opens the door of uncertainty and it fears man. The uncertainties in life make man aware that existence is his full responsibility. Man is confronted by the fact that his existence is his alone, its burden lies on his own shoulder and by this, man has an inviolable task to look for his own meaning. What fears man is the reality that he is alone in facing the void – his own existence. Since existence does not have an innate meaning, to find one becomes a rigorous task, and by this, man despairs. The very experience of depression truly disturbs man, and instead of confronting this kind of disturbance, man begins to look for an escape, and man has succeeded through the anti-depressants.

Furthermore, for Mugathan et al. as quoted by Bongiorno (2015), "addiction to anxiety medication is also another problem, as drug induced changes in brain function lead to need for higher dosage, withdrawal symptoms and greater disability." Here, Bongiorno explores the exploitative effects of taking anti-depressant. For Bongiorno, the gradual intake of these medicines leads man to fully depend on it. Anti-depressant alienates man, they turn man into a slave. Addiction to anti-depressant can be considered as a form of alienation because it takes away man's autonomy. Once addicted, man has no longer the ability to resist, instead desires it more. The volition of man has been separated from man's being. Also, addiction to anti-depressant may cause other physiological problem. That is why instead of fixing the problem, it gets worst.

Furthermore, aside from scientific remedies, another approach commonly used today to address depression is "psychotherapy." Unlike medical science, psychotherapy does not use drugs or shock treatments; instead, it uses talk therapy, also known as counseling. In this method, there are two fundamental elements involved; the first is the counselor, who serves as the facilitator, the second is the client, s/he is considered the depressed person. In psychotherapy, the counselor allows the depressed person to open up and bring out what burdens him. Psychotherapy believes that a person suffers from depression because they cannot bring out the burden within. A depressed person has no one to speak with and no one to lean on, which is what psychotherapy is trying to address. In this method, the counselor journeys with a depressed person until he fully understands the real issue and realizes why he feels that way. In psychotherapy, a client is the one who will discover solutions to his problems by having a clear grasp of the situation with the help of the counselor. Psychotherapy seems to be a more edifying and enlivening approach than that of science. However, psychotherapy is a

very limited approach because it only addresses the current issue encountered by the person and not the quality of living as a whole. Psychotherapy cannot really address the tragic reality of life. The coping mechanism being provided by the counselor during the therapy is clearly intended only to cope certain life issues, for example separation, but not really the very tragedy of life itself which is the origin of the problem of meaning. Though it is true that certain situations may contribute to the occurrence of depression, nevertheless, these situations are not the actual reasons themselves. Separation for instance depresses man not because man is separated from a person he loved, but it is greatly because this situation brings him the sense of meaninglessness. Mere understanding of the situation itself does not truly touch the reality of the loss of meaning. As what Soren Kierkegaard notes, "despair is never ultimately over the external object but always of ourselves . . . we stand denuded and see the intolerable abyss of ourselves" (Murray, 1974, p. 17). Taking these words, depression is something that requires personal resolve – a creation of man's own meaning.

Furthermore, the burden in psychotherapy does not only lie on the depressed person, but also in the therapist. The success of the process in achieving its goal is dependent on how well and accurate the interpretation of the therapist on the issue. The problem nonetheless is, unlike science, in which the basis of the finding are objective phenomena, in psychotherapy, it lies on individual's personal experiences of the world that includes emotions, perspectives, and others alike which are susceptible to misinterpretation and biases. This may imply that the therapist may render a subjective understanding of the problem. In this case, the therapist may not able to yield a clear grasp of the problem brought by the depressed person, and therefore, the coping mechanism which possibly be endorsed to the depressed person might not able to help him. How can this be overcome? The simplest answer is, to adopt an objective model in analyzing each issue and give objective responses. However, if it is to be done, another problem may arise, objectifying the therapy goes against the very nature of conducting the psychotherapy. Why? It is because, each problem is in itself unique and therefore requires unique solution. The objectification of the method as well as its solutions is tantamount to objectification of man, in which, should not happen in the psychotherapy. To objectify man only means that man is reducible into objective material, depriving man his or her creative dimensions. Fideler (2002) "warned that psychotherapist may be coercive and impose ideas at illness and wellness, which may undermine an individual's personal needs and integrity (p.1, cited in Knapp & Tjeltveit, 2005, p. 562).

That is why for Nietzsche, regardless of all the existing solutions for depression, as long as a person does not know how to embrace that the general sense of life is a tragedy, man will always encounter despair. Like taking medications, psychotherapy may ease depression for a while, yet it will again knock on man's door. As Ruggiero (2001) writes, "depression goes beyond psychological dysfunction, it is not some evil that needs to be extirpated from the mind or some disease that needs to be palliated by drugs, it might be an embodiment of philosophical pessimism, a natural reaction to one's social surrounding and situation."

Philosophically speaking, no drugs can mend depression. The truth is, depression is caused by a particular realization about the reality of existence. As discussed in the previous paragraphs, for Nietzsche, humans get depressed because they have seen the ugly truth of life—that his very existence is a tragedy, an inescapable reality. Though humans are indeed gifted with freedom and become capable of designing what kind of life they want to live, life has certain facticity that even freedom cannot conquer, "life is ugly" is thereby one of these facts. The desire to be happy, as mentioned, is only a temporary replacement for the horror and terror of life; nevertheless, when this replacement subsides, humans will again stand in the absurdity of existence. As humans face existence, they realize that happiness is not absolute; what is conclusive is that life is miserable, and this is what depresses them. Given the reality of life's tragedy, it seems that existence has no meaning at all for a human. For Nietzsche, however, to speak of meaninglessness is a concrete manifestation of man's resignation. As Nietzsche sees it, depression happens because humans force themselves to escape life's tragedy, which is an impossible task. Opposite to how a depressed person sees the world, Nietzsche believes that the tragedy of life is an essential element for becoming. Instead of losing a sense of meaning, for Nietzsche, the horror and terror of existence must opt humans to search more for meaning. As Nietzsche argues, it is pointless to resist life's ugly reality; instead, it is only by having enough courage to gaze to this truth that life is won. As Soren Kierkegaard once noted, "life without suffering is no life at all." Thus for Nietzsche, it is only by facing the obstacles in life that man fully lives. Only by living life amidst its horror and terror does that human overcomes depression and transforms his entire existence into art. For Nietzsche, what saves man from the tragedy and despair of life is to live "aesthetically," and this is what Nietzsche calls "aesthetic experience."

As Nietzsche contends, meaning can only be found when a man sees existence and all its events and experiences as the interplay of art. Nietzsche sees modernism as the iconoclasm of meaning as modernism rejects the value of things that are irrational as they believed to mislead man in his search for truth. The founding fathers of modernism believe that only through reason truth is grasped; thus, things that do not pass through the inquiry of human reason cannot be taken as true. The modernistic culture has transformed the entire period into an era of dogmatism, that nothing is more important than objective and absolute truth. The movement which had been started by Socrates and continued to grow during the time of Descartes was convinced that what gave sense to man's existence was his love for truth. Rationalist philosophers argued that man in nature was a thinking being and therefore man's very essence was to obtain the truth. However, for Nietzsche, rationalists' fascination to reason and truth is truly vomiting. As discussed, Nietzsche has denounced the truth conceived by science, for him truth is only a fabrication of man. As Nietzsche believes in speaking of objective and absolute truth murders man's creativity, and upon the death of man's creativity is also the death of meaning. The emergence of objective truth forces humans to conform to such truth, so to speak, humans must abide by the system in general, consequently, forcing them to set aside their individuality. The idea of truth alienates the person and turns them into a slave. Humans must act in accordance with what has been prescribed based on the conceived objective and absolute truth, and because of this, human individuality and creativity are

suppressed. This is the very reason why Nietzsche goes against the culture of modernity and makes ancient Greek literature the very foundation of his entire philosophical project because, as Nietzsche sees it, ancient Greek literature is so overloaded with beauty and art. As Nietzsche (1872/2003) believes, "only as an aesthetic phenomenon our existence and the world eternally justified" (p. 18). Here, only through art can depression be addressed. If there is truth, for Nietzsche, that truth must be grounded on human creativity.

In *The Birth of Tragedy*, Nietzsche (1872/2003) writes, "art and not morality was the essential metaphysical human activity . . . that the existence of the world is justified only as an aesthetic phenomenon" (p. 4). Here, a question can be asked, how can a human transform their life into art in which meaning can be found and depression can be addressed? For Nietzsche, art is possible through binding up the Apollonian and Dionysian forces; it is because, for Nietzsche, the interaction of the Apollonian and Dionysian forces produces balance and gives birth to life. As Nietzsche himself explains, the god Apollo from whom Apollonian force radiates symbolizes perfection, harmony, order, and joy. Apollo is the representation of light. His countenance means abundance. As mentioned in the previous chapter, Apollo is the redemptive god. As Nietzsche illustrates, Apollo is also considered the god of reason, consciousness, and moderation; he is a reflection of truth. Apollo exhibits the positivity of existence and wellness. As written, "Apollo is the god of prophecy, a representation of brightness, the god of light" (Nietzsche, 1872/2003, p. 9). Dionysus, on the other hand, is considered the opposite of Apollo. Dionysus, as Nietzsche explains, is the god of destruction, excess, and rapture. He is the god of wine, and so symbolizes intoxication and passion. Dionysus is a carefree god who finds delight in festivals and celebrations, a god filled with emotions, thus illustrating irrationality. Unlike Apollo, Dionysus is a paradoxical god because he is both a god of suffering and joy. As noted in the previous chapter, Dionysus can cause madness to anyone he encounters, but as Otto (1965) argues, "the madness of Dionysus does not bring impairment, but life at its healthiest." The very being of Dionysus is truly susceptible to negative interpretation, but as Nietzsche sees it, the being of Dionysus is the perfect mirror of human existence. Dionysus reveals the reality of what it means to live—that life is both suffering and joy, destruction and creation, fall and redemption. The brute force that emanates from Dionysus only shows Dionysus's ability to break the monotonous phasing of life; he has total control of his very existence. The intoxication attributed to Dionysus does not mean being a total drunkard but a reflection that life is joyful. What Nietzsche finds in the being of Dionysus are dynamism, liveliness, and abundance. For Nietzsche, Dionysus is the god who sees all the dimensions of existence. Amidst his struggles, Dionysus has emerged victorious. Existence does not only mean living; to truly exist means facing all the odds in life, which is what Dionysus means. For Nietzsche, Dionysus is the epitome of great health," which was being exhibited by the Greek culture, as Nietzsche (1889) puts it, "the saying yes to life in its strangest and hardest problems; the will to live, that's what I call Dionysian." For Nietzsche, the intercourse of the Apollonian and Dionysian forces gives birth to art.

Furthermore, depression can only be resolved when human knows how to live artistically. By embodying both the Apollonian and the Dionysian forces, a human can live fully amidst the sorrow and ugliness of life. What does it mean? Humans must learn how to be rational, clear, and enlightened (Apollonian) while being emotive, passionate, and joyous (Dionysian). For Nietzsche, because man has allowed himself to be consumed by science and modernity, human sees the Dionysian forces as nonsense and only disturbances of life, and so neglected.

Consequently, human has forgotten how to live artistically. Life is already a curse, and for Nietzsche, without art, it becomes more miserable, which leads to depression. As mentioned, the fundamental reason why human falls into the pit of depression is the ugly truth of life—its absurdity. However, by embodying the Apollonian and Dionysian forces, man could possess the character of the Greeks, who could always find ways to celebrate life amidst its horror and terror. To live artistically means embodying what Nietzsche calls "great health." By great health, Nietzsche implies a person's capability and character to face all the contradictions in existence, which is what living aesthetically is about. To live artistically allows man to embrace life as what it is without disgust. A human who learns how to live aesthetically does not abhor his existence; instead, he befriends it in spite and despite its ugliness, and this is what Nietzsche calls "Amor Fati" or "love of fate."

The origin of depression can be traced from the act of hating existence, but as for Nietzsche, only when a person embraces both the blessings and curses of life that one fully lives. As Nietzsche (1887/2001) says, "I want to learn more and more how to see what is necessary in things as what is beautiful in them, thus I will be one of those who make things beautiful . . . and all in all and on the whole: someday I want only to be a Yes-sayer!" (p. 157). It is clear then that for Nietzsche, only by saying yes to life amidst its difficulties, meaning in existence can be found, and depression can be avoided only by this. As Riess quoted Siegel: "[U]nless we can see the world aesthetically, we're going to see it at times as dull, as against us, or so much better than us. Unless the person is ready to say, come on world, affect me more! He is planning depression" (2009). Many philosophers think that Nietzsche is a nihilist; nonetheless, by being a nihilist, Nietzsche does not intend to destroy but to give a new hope in which the fullness of life can be stood. As Nietzsche (1872/2003) writes:

Lift up your heads, my brothers, high, higher! And for my sake don't forget your legs! Raise up your legs, you fine dancers, and better yet, stand on your heads! This crown of man who laughs, this crown wreathed with roses – I have placed this crown on myself. I speak out my holy laughter to myself. Today I found no one else strong for that. This crown of the laughing man, this crown of rose wreaths; my brothers I throw this crown to you! Laughter I declare secret; you higher men, for my sake learn to laugh. (pp. 6-7)

As discussed, depression is not a kind of mental anomaly that must be suppressed. It is a force that echoes humans, telling them to take a break from the tedious unfolding of life. Depression is a force that calls humans to overcome their present state of existence and

transform it to the full. Nietzsche suggests that only by learning how to see the beauty and live with them, instead of dwelling on what is ugly, can humans redeem their selves from the phenomenon of depression.

Furthermore, Nietzsche contends that only by living aesthetically can humans be able to transcend. Nietzsche himself argues that only by seeing the existence as a manifestation of art does that human becomes a superior being. As mentioned in the previous chapter, only the superior being can gaze at the horror and terror of existence and still finds the courage and strength to live, thus, emerging herself or himself victorious. In *Thus Spoke Zarathustra*, Nietzsche identifies two kinds of man, the first one is the "ubermensch" or "overman," and the second one is the "last man." As explained by Nietzsche, the *ubermensch* refers to the superior man who has managed to transcend and overcome himself. According to Kaplama (2016), "self-overcoming requires the *ubermensch* to become the abundant flow and relentless change with all its resulting chaos and madness, the most essential prerequisite for an artistic and creative transformation (p. 206)." Therefore, it can be argued from Nietzsche's point of view that the *ubermensch* is the embodiment of both Apollonian and Dionysian forces. The *ubermensch* is Nietzsche's illustration of someone whose very existence is transformed into art. The *ubermensch* is a concrete manifestation of what Nietzsche calls "great health." Cybulska quotes aphorism 382 of the *Gay Science*, "the *ubermensch* advocates a new great health which he equates with an all-embracing totality whereby all opposites are blended into a unity" (2012). Here, by embodying both Apollonian and Dionysian forces, the *ubermensch* can perceive life holistically, enabling him to celebrate life amidst all its vicissitudes.

What about the last man? As Nietzsche (1885/1954) writes, "the time is coming when man will no longer give birth to a star, the time of the most despicable man is coming . . . behold, I show you the last man" (p. 5). The last man is the complete opposite of the *ubermensch*. The last man, as Nietzsche explains, is someone who has no desire to transcend and overcome the self instead finds joy in being stagnant. The last man believes that there is nothing more in existence than by just living. The last man lives as how others live. His values are that of others and not truly of himself. The last man is the man of the crowd; his identity lies on others; he has no individuality. The last man wishes to be everyone.

As Nietzsche argues, the last man is someone who does not know how to live aesthetically. In *Thus Spoke Zarathustra*, Nietzsche (1885/1954) writes, "What is ape to man? A laughing stock or a painful embarrassment. And man shall be just that for the overman; a laughing stock or a painful embarrassment" (p. 3). Now, the last man is an inferior being for the *ubermensch*, and for such reason, Nietzsche recognizes the need for man to transcend himself. For Nietzsche, if a man truly desires to obtain the meaning of his existence, man must break his conventional self and embrace the burden of becoming an *ubermensch*. Nietzsche believes that *ubermensch* must be the finality of man.

It has been mentioned that only by living artistically can humans break depression. Since the *ubermensch* is the embodiment of artistic existence, it can be argued that by becoming an *ubermensch*, depression can be fixed. By becoming an *ubermensch*, a human can obtain more than enough courage and strength to stand in the face of existence amidst its horror and terror. As written, "one must have chaos in oneself to be able to give birth to a dancing star" (Nietzsche, 1885/1954, p. 5). In addition, existence is always a riddle that only humans alone can solve. With this, a human must find their way to conquer life; it is here that being artistic comes into the picture. As an existentialist, Nietzsche would say that there is no single formula for dealing with existence; it is something that humanity has to figure out alone. Nietzsche would say that human designs his own life, and it only intends to mean that life in itself is an art. And for Nietzsche, to be an *ubermensch* means to be able to transform life to what it truly is, art. By transforming oneself into an *ubermensch*, depression can be avoided.

Furthermore, Nietzsche argues that aesthetic life and will to power are and should be inseparable elements necessary for man to overcome all the horror and terrors of existence. Will to power is considered the fundamental force that allows existence to be possible, "it is the characteristic of everything that lives" (Nietzsche, 1885/1954, p.1). The continuous survival of the species requires the will to power; it drives every living being to continue to choose existence amidst its harsh condition. Every existence is an act of will to power. For Nietzsche, artistic existence requires the will to power; only with the will to power can man truly assert himself that he can become a true free spirit capable of creating his meaning and values.

Fundamentally, depression happens because man allows himself to be driven by ugly realities of life. Human fails to determine his course. But with the will to power, a person can able to assert their own life. Humans can be able to stir the course of their existence. Man does not allow the horror and terror of existence to govern him, however with the will to power, man can emancipate himself from these forces of his existence. With the will to power, the maximization of individual freedom is possible, which gives man the ability to break himself from the herd, from being determined.

Nietzsche has so much faith in individual freedom. For Nietzsche, no one can save man from the tragedy of life but himself or herself. In the *Thus Spoke Zarathustra*, Nietzsche claims, "God is Dead," and by this, man is left alone. Nietzsche's idea of the death of God paves way for man to fully exercise his will to power. This time, no Supreme Being controls man. Man now fully controls himself or herself. Does the death of God in Nietzsche's thought authorize man to be a savage being? As what Fyodor Dostoyevsky notes, "if God did not exist, everything would be permitted" (Maboloc, 2013, p. 7). However, Nietzsche does not settle on this idea. The idea that God is dead is a symbolic critique of Nietzsche towards the established norm and standards of what is good and evil, which for Nietzsche very dogmatic and striped away from man the capacity to decide on his or her own what is good and evil. Nietzsche's intention is not to discard the reality of good and evil, instead to remind man of his power to identify and create what is truly good for

himself and not just to a conformist to the status quo. An aesthetic man who fully exercises the will to power has the ability to create his own standard of what is good and evil, and holds responsible for them. An aesthetic man, a *ubermensch* knows what needs to be done. With will to power, man has the ability to stir his own fate opposite to a fate coined by norms and others' beliefs. For Nietzsche, man must learn to create his or her own values and live with them. Nietzsche also believes that an aesthetic man is also a moral man.

As an existentialist, Nietzsche contends that human has no innate and pre-determined essences, following this thought; the self is an open possibility. A person cannot be reduced to the alienating objective structure of the external world. The meaning of human existence is something not found, instead created, and only through the full maximization of will to power that this quest is possible. Existentialism, though not directly stated, speaks of the entire existence as a work of art. Since the burden of existence lies to no one but to the humans, no pre-existing values nor essences, they have all the power to create their own meaning based on what they think and see relevant, and this is what to live aesthetically is about. Though existence is something that a human does not choose for her or himself, yet with the will to power, they can always find a reason to choose existence and see it as something delightful amidst its difficulties. Nietzsche's entire philosophical project is meant to awaken humans of what it means to live. Nietzsche's criticisms against modernity, science, and religion are all because he simply wants to restore the liveliness and thrill of existence, which is forgotten that leads to man's restlessness and loss of meaning. For Nietzsche, the truth which man searches is not the truth grounded on knowledge and facts but the truth that must be rooted on man's aesthetic experience. Nietzsche's aesthetic experience is deeply rooted on his fascination to how the early Greek culture and society dealt with life, and his call to live like the Greeks remains.

What should man undergo to embody what Nietzsche calls aesthetic life and to address the phenomenon of depression? Basically, there is no immediate remedy for depression. Science and even psychology would admit that in order to get rid of depression, man has to undergo certain process. Unlike science and psychology, Nietzsche's aesthetic experience does not intend to address the superficial issues that may cause depression, instead it attempts to address the core cause – meaninglessness. On one hand, it is possible that when someone is depressed, he or she may suffer from neural dysfunction which can be properly addressed by science. On the other hand, it is also possible that when man faces real life issues like separation, man gets depressed and that, psychology is of great aid. Moreover, behinds all these issues, there lies the greater one – meaning. For Nietzsche, man has to live an aesthetic life if he or she wishes to find his or her own meaning.

In the *Thus Spoke Zarathustra*, Zarathustra desires to teach the *ubermensch*. Nietzsche's intention is not just to lay down what it means to be a *ubermensch* but also how to be the *ubermensch* himself or herself. Therefore, in Nietzsche line of thinking, a depressed person has to yield a character that embraces both the Apollonian and the Dionysian quality to transform himself or herself into art, which is comprised of these stages; first – “the re-evaluation of one's perspective in life. In this stage, the depressed person has to examine how his or her life is going. He needs to be enlightened to identify the things he or she values as well as aware of the things that give him or her burden. By doing this, it would become handy for him or her to understand his or her own situation. Man has to clear his or her sight where his or her life is leading to. Here, the depressed person digs out the reason of his or her own meaninglessness. In this stage, the person has to obtain a clear and real picture of how his or her life appears to him or her and by doing so, the person finds the necessity to untangle himself from his current situation and shall create a new one. Second – “infusing of Nietzsche's thoughts.” In this stage, the depressed person will be oriented and will learn what Nietzsche means with aesthetic living. A depressed person has to have a real grasp of the reality of existence, its tragic truth and how can this be overcome with aesthetic approach towards life. A depressed person has to learn the essence of Apollo and Dionysian forces and their balance in facing the absurdity of life. In this stage, the depressed person will learn how to become a *ubermensch*. Third – “practice.” In this stage, the person will now embody what he learns from Nietzsche's philosophical treatise. Man now begins to put into action what Nietzsche means with authentic life. However, this is not immediate, rather a gradual process of paradigm shift. Here, the person will exercise moderation and balance between being rational and emotive. The person becomes assertive and live with his or her own will. He or she does not allow other people to dictate the course of his or her life, instead he or she dictates him or her own self. He or she begins to do the things he or she wants to do and take responsibility over them. He or she now creates and determines his or her life course and values. He or she begins to re-create him or herself based on what he or she truly desires that lead him or her to find his or her own meaning. By learning and living an aesthetic life, depression can be overcome. Man should live like the Greeks.

By criticizing both science and psychology, it does not mean a total rejection of these means, however, there is something more about depression that goes beyond the realm of science and psychology, and that is the problem of meaning. More so, this paper does not want to assume that Nietzsche's aesthetic experience can be the answer to all psychological and mental problem. This paper wants to maintain that the phenomenon of depression has something to do with man's search for meaning, and thus, Nietzsche's aesthetic philosophy is of great help.

Conclusion

Unlike other beings, humans believe that there is something more in existence than just the mere survival of their species. Humans are aware not only of the things around them but also of themselves. They desire to know the very reason why they exist or why they are here; this desire is tantamount to man's search for meaning. Most of what humans do is directed towards the attainment of meaning. However, failing to do so leads man into despair. As mentioned, depression is a kind of mental disorder characterized by unstable mood, loss of interest or pleasure, decreased energy, feeling of guilt, low self-worth . . . and may lead to suicide (WHO, 2012). It cannot

be denied that today, depression has become a phenomenon that confronts many people. This occurrence is not a simple problem; it affects the person entirely-- physically, emotionally, and socially. For a depressed person, nothing will make sense anymore.

Intellectuals from objective science are convinced that the fundamental cause of depression is a chemical/hormonal imbalance taking place in the brain. For this, objective science prescribes different medicines to restore the balance in the brain to end a person's depression. Amidst the existing plethora of scientific and medicinal interventions, depression continues to persist. What does objective science fail to address?

Philosophically speaking, existentialist philosophers recognize that life is not purely milk and honey; for them, the truth of life is bitter. Existentialist thinkers argue that life is ugly—an undeniable fact—and because of this, man begins to find life nauseating, thereby rejecting it. For existentialist philosophers, the very reason a person despair is not the neural dysfunction but rather their in-depth realization of the absurdity of life, the failure to see the essential meaning of life. Friedrich Nietzsche, belonging to the existentialist tradition, agrees that life in itself is replete with suffering; however, for him, life does not end there. For Nietzsche, only when a person enables to embrace the absurdity of life fully can he or she put an end to his or her experience of depression. However, the question is how? Nietzsche's simple answer is by learning how to live one's life aesthetically. Nietzsche himself considers the facts provided by science as not the basis of any truths as these are merely a description of how the world appears to be. With this, it can be said that for Nietzsche, how science understands the phenomenon of depression and its solutions are superficial compared to what depression is. The absurdity of life, which is the core reason for man's depression, can never be remedied by medical science. For Nietzsche, the absurdity of life can only be overcome (and life's meaning is possible) when man learns how to live his life with capability to stir his course, assert himself, and create his values. What does it mean to live aesthetically? For Nietzsche, to live aesthetically means to be able to harmonize both the Apollonian (rational) and Dionysian (passion) forces that are both embedded in the being of a person. Being able to uphold both reason and passion turns man to become what it means to be human. By embracing both the Apollonian and Dionysian forces, man turns himself into *Übermensch* who exercises his will to power. This will to power allows man to exercise his own freedom and has full control of his own destiny. An *Übermensch* is someone who is capable of gazing and embracing the tragic life even how ugly it is. Only an *Übermensch* can remain faithful to life and love it amidst its horrific picture. Only by becoming an *Übermensch* that life is lived aesthetically. When it comes to the problem of depression, Nietzsche suggests that only by seeing life aesthetically that it can be truly solved. By embracing willingly, the reality of life as both a blessing and curse, meaning is obtained and depression is avoided. Accepting life as it is, is what Nietzsche means "aesthetic life."

Nietzsche sees the importance of passion in man's life, which has been trivialized by modernism. For Nietzsche, to be an aesthetic person is to be a free spirit while at the same time availing himself of the power of reason within himself. Thus, to be an aesthetic person is also to be a rational one. Only through seeing life this way and having this character man can overcome depression. It can be concluded that "only as an aesthetic phenomenon that our existence and the world are eternally justified" (Nietzsche, 1872/2003, p. 18).

References

- Abbagnano, N. (n.d.). Existentialism. Retrieved from <https://www.britannica.com/topic/existentialism>.
- Anokhina, A. (2016). Authenticity and treatment for depression. Retrieved from https://philosophynow.org/issues/115/Authenticity_and_Treatment_For_Depression
- Anxiety and Depression Association of America (n.d.). Depression. Retrieved from www.adaa.org.
- Baker, J. (2011). Nietzsche on knowledge, truth, and life: Nietzsche's criticisms of Christianity. Claremont Graduate University, School of Religion.
- Bolea, S. (2014). What is existentialism? A revision of contemporary definitions. *Studia UBB, Philosophia*, 59 (2), 63-72. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/>
- Bongiorno, P.B. (2015). *Holistic solutions for anxiety & depression in therapy*. New York: W.W. Norton & Company.
- Colter, R.S. (2017). How the stoicism of Roman philosophers can help us deal with depression (Online Article). University of Wyoming. Retrieved from <https://theconersation.com>
- Daniel, V. (2013). Existentialism: Its evolution and how it applies today. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/>.
- Durr, C. (2018). What existentialism can teach us about dealing with depression. Retrieved from <https://hackernoon.com>
- Elliot, C.H., PhD & Smith, L.L., PhD (2006). *Anxiety & depression workbook for dummies*. Indianapolis, Indiana: Wiley Publishing, Inc.
- Gelonesi, J. (n.d.). To describe the indescribable: A philosophy of depression. Retrieved from <https://www.abc.net.au/radionational/programs/philosopherzone>
- Gerhardt, V. (n.d.). Philosophizing against Philosophy: Nietzsche's provocation of the philosophical tradition. Retrieved from

<http://www.hunter.cuny.edu/>

Gholipour, B. (2017). Depression: Causes, symptoms and treatments. Retrieved from <https://www.livescience.com/34718-depression-treatment-psychotherapy-anti-depressants.html>

Grech, G. J. (2010). Aristotle's Eudaimonia and two conceptions of happiness. University of St. Andrews. Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net>

Hall, J.H., (2016). Slanted truths: the gay science as Nietzsche's ars poetica. *evental aesthetics*, 5, (1), 98-117

Hasbanyah, O. (2002). The search for meaning of life: Existentialism, communication and Islam. *Mediator*, 3 (2), 249-258.

Hassall, D.J. (2017). Finding Meaning in the Lack Thereof: An Analysis of Nietzsche's and Sartre's Responses to the Problem of Existential Nihilism (Honors Thesis). Eastern Kentucky University. Retrieved from https://encompass.eku.edu/honors_theses/493

Iyer, K. & Khan, Z.A. (2012). Depression – A review. *Research Journal of Recent Sciences*, 1(4), 78-87. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/>

Iwuagwu, E.K. (2017). Martin Heidegger and the question of being. *Journal of Integrative Humanism*, 8 (1), 25-48. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/>

Kaplama, E. (2016). Kantian and Nietzschean aesthetics of human nature: A comparison between the beautiful/sublime and Apollonian/Dionysian dualities. *The Journal of Natural and Social Philosophy*, 12 (1), 166-217.

Knapp, S., & Tjeltveit, A. (2005). A review and critical analysis of philosophical counseling. *Professional Psychology: Research and Practice*, 36 (5), 558–565. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/>

Laderoute, K. L. (2013). *Between modern and post-modern: Nietzsche on truth and knowledge*. Hamilton, Ontario: McMaster University.

Leiter, B. (1992). Nietzsche and aestheticism. *Journal of the History of Philosophy*, 30, 275-290. Retrieved from http://chicagounbound.uchicago.edu/journal_articles

Livni, E. (2019). Feeling anxious? It's not just you, it's our philosophical era of neuroexistentialism. Retrieved from <https://qz.com>

Maboloc, C.R.B., (2013). *Philosophy of man: The existential drama fundamental topics and thinkers*, (Rev. ed). St., Sta. Mesa Heights, Quezon City, Philippines: Rex Printing Company, Inc. Florentino

Murray, M. K. (1974). *An existential conceptualization of depression as an escape from responsibility* (Doctoral Thesis, Montana State University, 1974). Bozeman, Montana: Montana State University.

National Institute of Mental Health (2016). Depression basics. Retrieved from www.nimh.nih.gov.

Nietzsche, F. (1889). *Twilight of the idols* (Rev. Ed.). Leipzig, Germany: Penguin Classic.

Nietzsche, F. (1911). *Ecce homo*. (A.M. Ludovici, Trans.). New York: The Macmillan Company. (Original Work Published 1888).

Nietzsche, F. (1954). *Thus spoke Zarathustra* (Walter Kaufmann, Trans.). Viking Penguin Inc. (Original Work Published 1885).

Nietzsche, F. (1966). *Beyond good and evil* (Walter Kaufmann, Trans.). New York: Vintage Books. (Original Work Published 1886).

Nietzsche, F. (2001). *The gay science*, Bernard Williams, (Ed.), (Josefine Nauckhoff and Adrian Del Caro, Trans.). New York: Cambridge University Press. Cambridge. (Original Work Published 1887).

Nietzsche, F. (2003). *The birth of tragedy* (Ian Johnston, Trans.). Canada: Malaspina University-College. Nanaimo, BC. (Original Work Published 1872).

Nietzsche, F. (n.d.). *On the genealogy of morals* (Ian Johnston, Trans.). Canada: Malaspina University-College. Nanaimo, BC. (Original Work Published 1887).

Nietzsche, F. (1976). 'On truth and lies in a nonmoral sense' in the portable Nietzsche, Walter Kaufmann, (Ed.). New York: Viking Press. (Original Work Published 1896).

Otto, W.F. (1965). *Dionysus: Myth and cult* (Robert B. Palmer, Trans.). North Morton Street, Bloomington, USA: Indiana University Press. <http://www.indiana.edu/~iupress>

Popova, M. (n.d.). www.brainpickings.org. Retrieved March 11, 2019.

Reiss, E. (2009). Aesthetics; or, how not to be depressed. *A Periodical of Hope and Information*. Retrieve from <http://aestheticrealism.net/tro/aesthetics-or-how-not-to-be-depressed/#lecture>.

Ruggiero, T. (2001). Philosophy and depression. Retrieved from <https://philosophicalsociety.com/Archives/Philosophy>.

Ryan, R. M., & Martela, F. (n.d.). Eudaimonia as a way of living: Connecting Aristotle with self-determination theory. Australian Catholic University, Institute for Positive Psychology and Education.

Torres, F., M.D., MBA, DFAPA (2020). What is depression? Retrieved from <https://www.psychiatry.org/patients-families/depression/what-is-depression>.

Vieth, D. (2013). Existentialism: Its evolution and how it applies today.

What causes depression? Onset of depression more complex than a brain chemical imbalance (2009). Retrieved from <https://www.health.harvard.edu/mind-and-mood/what-causes-depression>.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Ypril James F. Cabasag

University of Southern Mindanao – Philippines